

Comparative Experimental Analysis of Biogas Recovery Rate from Anaerobic Digestion of Single and Multiple Organic Feedstock

Aniekan Essienubong Ikpe¹, Ekerete William Nkom², Michael Okon Bassey³

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering Technology, Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua

² Department of Welding and Fabrication Engineering Technology, Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua

³ Department of Mechatronics Engineering Technology, Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua

ARTICLE INFO

©2025 RS Publication

Paper ID: IJASTR-689E15D3B9ADF

Received: 2025-07-15

Published: 2025-08-19

DOI:
<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16900447>

Page No: 240-253

ABSTRACT

Renewable energy is not only one of the main drivers of greenhouse gas mitigation but a pivot that contributes to the achievement of sustainable development goals. This research presents a comparative experimental analysis of biogas recovery rates from anaerobic digestion (AD) of single and multiple organic feedstocks, aimed at optimizing renewable energy generation and waste management strategies. Using an 82 L batch-type bio-digester, controlled experiments were conducted on food waste (single feedstock) and a combination of food waste with other varieties of organic substrates (multiple feedstocks) under mesophilic conditions over a 28-day hydraulic retention time (HRT). Parameters monitored included biogas yield, digester temperature, and pH at three daily evacuation times (10:00 am, 2:00 pm, and 6:00 pm). Results revealed that co-digestion of multiple feedstocks achieved higher average and peak biogas yields (0.23–0.24 g) compared to single feedstock (0.21–0.22 g), with an 8–10% yield improvement and faster ramp-up to peak production. Multiple feedstocks also maintained higher and more stable digester temperatures (30–31 °C) than single feedstock (26–29 °C), indicating enhanced microbial activity and process stability. Optimal yields were consistently recorded at 6:00 pm across both configurations, likely due to cumulative gas build-up. The findings underscore the operational advantages of co-digestion, including improved substrate balance, enhanced methanogenesis, and sustained thermal performance, while highlighting the need for monitoring to mitigate potential inhibitory effects. This study is one of the sustainability strategies that supports the adoption of multi-feedstock AD systems for maximizing biogas productivity and advancing sustainable energy recovery from organic waste.

Keywords: Anaerobic digestion, Biogas yield, Co-digestion, Single feedstock, Multiple feedstocks, Renewable energy

Cite This Paper : Aniekan Essienubong Ikpe, Ekerete William Nkom and Michael Okon Bassey (2025). "Comparative Experimental Analysis of Biogas Recovery Rate from Anaerobic Digestion of Single and Multiple Organic Feedstock". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL RESEARCH (IJASTR)* ISSN 2249-9954, vol. 15, no.4,2025, pp. 240-253. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16900447>

1. Introduction

The growing global population and increasing urbanization have led to a significant rise in organic waste generation. Simultaneously, the urgent need to mitigate climate change has driven the search for alternative, renewable energy sources (Ebunilo et al., 2018). Anaerobic digestion (AD) offers a unique solution to both these challenges by converting organic waste into biogas, a renewable energy source primarily composed of methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) (Qian et al., 2025; Gabanki, 2025). AD is a biological process that breaks down organic matter in the absence of oxygen, producing biogas as a valuable by-product. This process has gained significant attention in recent years as a sustainable method for waste management and renewable energy production (Ezeh et al., 2024; Serna-García et al., 2025). Biogas, primarily composed of methane and carbon dioxide, can be used as a renewable fuel source for heat and electricity generation. The efficiency of biogas production through AD depends on various factors, including the type and composition of the organic feedstock used (Ibrahim et al., 2025; Ochuko, 2025). Traditionally, many AD systems have relied on single feedstocks, such as agricultural waste, food waste, or sewage sludge. However, there is growing interest in the co-digestion of multiple organic feedstocks to potentially enhance biogas yield and improve process stability. Biogas production through AD of organic feedstocks has gained significant attention in recent years as a sustainable and environmentally friendly approach to waste management and renewable energy generation (Kim & Kim, 2025; Milicevic et al., 2025). This process harnesses the natural metabolic activities of microorganisms to break down organic matter in the absence of oxygen, resulting in the production of a methane-rich biogas and a nutrient-rich digestate. The increasing global focus on reducing greenhouse gas emissions, managing organic waste, and transitioning towards circular economy principles has propelled research and implementation of AD technologies across various sectors (Dasgupta, 2025; Makondo et al., 2025). AD is a complex, multi-stage process involving hydrolysis, acidogenesis, acetogenesis, and methanogenesis. Each stage is carried out by different groups of microorganisms working in syntrophic relationships (Simeonov et al., 2025; Perera et al., 2025). The efficiency and stability of the AD process depend on various factors, including feedstock composition, temperature, pH, organic loading rate, and hydraulic retention time (Zhu et al., 2025; Dhaouefi et al., 2025). Traditionally, AD has been applied to single organic feedstocks, such as agricultural residues, food waste, or sewage sludge. However, the use of single substrates often presents challenges related to nutrient imbalances, inhibitory compounds, or unfavourable carbon-to-nitrogen ratios. To address these limitations and enhance biogas production, scientists in the field have increasingly been beginning to explore the potentials of co-digesting multiple organic feedstocks. Co-digestion, the simultaneous AD of two or more substrates, offers several advantages over mono-digestion (Amoo et al., 2025; El-Sheikh et al., 2025). These benefits include improved nutrient balance, increased biodegradability, dilution of inhibitory compounds, enhanced microbial diversity, and ultimately, higher biogas yields. The synergistic effects of co-digestion can lead to more stable and efficient AD processes (Rhee et al., 2025; Saelor et al., 2025), making it an attractive option for waste management and renewable energy production. The selection of appropriate feedstock combinations for co-digestion is a critical aspect of optimizing biogas production. Factors such as availability, seasonality, chemical composition, and potential synergistic or antagonistic interactions between substrates must be carefully considered (Sani et al., 2025; Kamboj et al., 2025). Common co-digestion pairs include animal manure with crop residues, food waste with sewage sludge, and industrial organic waste with municipal solid waste. Recent advancements in AD technology have focused on enhancing process efficiency and stability through various pre-treatment methods, the use of additives, and the development of novel reactor designs (Woźniak et al., 2025; Silva

et al., 2025). These innovations aim to overcome challenges associated with recalcitrant feedstocks, improve methane yields, and reduce retention times. The biogas produced through AD has multiple applications, including direct use for heating and cooking, electricity generation through combined heat and power (CHP) systems, and upgrading to biomethane for injection into natural gas grids or use as a vehicle fuel (Kabeyi et al., 2025; Negro et al., 2025). The digestate, a by-product of the AD process, can be utilized as a valuable organic fertilizer, further contributing to the circular economy concept (Martín-Sanz-Garrido et al., 2025; Grobelak et al., 2025). As the world continues to grapple with the challenges of climate change, energy security, and sustainable waste management, biogas production from the AD of single and multiple organic feedstocks presents a promising solution. In recent times, a number of experimental investigations have been carried out in this field of studies, which have yielded significant outcomes that have contributed immensely to the body of knowledge on energy recovery from organic substrates. To examine the adequate biogas yield, Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) was adopted by Ikpe et al. (2020) for optimizing anaerobic co-digestion process parameters from organic feedstock (food waste and Pig slurry) at different mix ratios. Bio-digester temperature of 38°C, pH of 7.1, Hydraulic Retention Time (HRT) of 11 and mix ratio of 2:1 yielded overall highest biogas quantity of 247g from the experiment, whereas, process parameters of 40°C, pH of 7.1, HRT of 11 as well as mix ratio of 2:1 yielded maximum biogas of 248g. An experimental study was carried out by Ikpe et al. (2024), to evaluate the biogas yielding potential from anaerobic co-digestion of multiple feedstock including waterleaf, cow dung, and food waste. From the results, an average biogas yield of 25%, pH of 7.2 and C/N ratio of 28 were achieved from co-digestion of waterleaf and food waste, while 31% biogas yield, pH of 7.2, as well as C/N ratio of 29 were obtained from co-digestion of waterleaf and cow dung. However, biogas yield of 34%, pH of 7.1 and C/N ratio of 30 were achievable by combining food waste and cow dung in the experimental process while, 46% of biogas yield (which happened to be the highest), pH of 7 and C/N ratio of 32 were quantified from co-digestion of waterleaf, cow dung, and food waste. This indicates that the combination of multiple feedstock in AD process is more efficient in terms of the yielding rate, compared to single feedstock (Eronmosele et al., 2020; Ikpe et al., 2019). Borhany et al., (2025) conducted a comparable study on a novel line, comprising pre-treatment, acidogenic fermentation, as well as AD, with single-step AD considering the financial aspect and energy recovery in terms of biogas. Biogas yield was measured via gas chromatography. The findings revealed that 83% of the fermented volatile solids (VS) were processed into biogas to achieve methane (CH₄) yield of 0.133 Nm³/kg per volatile solids. Bewani et al., (2025) examined the performance of mechanical pre-treatment process, determining the composition of the residual waste, organic fraction recovery rate, and screw press efficiency for organic substrate recovery and biogas yield from the press water. The findings indicated 92% organic substrates recovery from residual waste, having subjected to shredding and trommel screening. High-quality press water with <3% inert materials (0.063-4 mm size) was obtained from the pressing process while mass balance analysis showed that 47% of fresh mass was extracted into press water, corresponding to 24% of VS obtained. Further evaluation revealed that the press water yielded 416 m³/ton VS biogas, producing 38% of the total biogas yield. A screening-level life cycle assessment (LCA) was carried out by Griggs et al. (2025), comparing the environmental impacts of these conventional end-of-life approach with AD technique. The AD technique was also examined for its energy potential by substituting bio-methane for traditional fossil fuels (natural gas and propane) employed in hemp biomass from cannabidiol production. The LCA suggested an operational AD efficiency of 60 %, yielding 286.7 mL CH₄/g volatile solids. The Comparative Experimental Analysis of Biogas Recovery Rate from AD of Single and Multiple Organic Feedstock in this study aims to evaluate and compare the efficiency of biogas production through AD processes using different types of organic materials. It is crucial for

advancing the understanding of AD process and optimizing biogas production. This plays a vital role in identifying the most effective combinations of organic materials for maximizing biogas yield, improving process stability, and enhancing overall system performance. The scope of the study includes conducting controlled experiments to measure and analyse the biogas yield, and production rate from various organic substrates when used individually (single feedstock) or in combination (multiple feedstocks or co-digestion).

2. Materials and Methods

The various materials used in the course of the experimental procedure in this study are stated as follows:

- a. **Samples:** Organic feedstocks such as food waste, waterleaf, Cow dung and distilled water. Variety of food waste were used during the experiment. These included the following: Soya beans, Rice, Cocoyam, Cooked Plantain, Semovita, Cooked Banana and Fufu. Samples of Cow dung co-digested during the experimental process of this study was collected from a Cattle market in Nasarawa, Afaha Oku, Uyo Local government area of Akwa Ibom State. The food wastes were sourced from different Cafeterias, Restaurants, Hotels, households in Benin City metropolis and its environs.
- b. The collected organic feedstock was homogenized and pretreated to expunge non-organic feedstocks which could serve as inhibitors against biogas yielding process. The pretreatment process involved sorting and segregation of organic contents from the non-organic contents. The next step in the pretreatment process was particle size reduction which involved shredding the feedstock into sizes that would not present challenges during disintegration by microbes. The next step involved homogenizing and mixing the segregated organic content prior to depositing them in the bio-digesters. This procedure was carried out differently for the single feedstock and the multiple feedstock. The single feedstock only contained food wastes, whereas, the multiple feedstock contained food waste, agricultural residues and animal manure. The experiment was carried out in a batch process, involving two different substrate combinations namely: single and multiple feedstocks.
- c. **Apparatus:** pH meter, stainless bowl, plastic pipes, rubber hose, bicycle tube ball valves, pressure gauge, digital thermometer, weighing scale and 82 liters plastic bio-digester. Plastic was selected as the bio-digester material because it can withstand corrosion effects and chemical reactions from the bio-thermal disintegration process). Also, bottom part of the bio-digester cover was insulated with foam to prevent leakage, minimize heat transfer and prevent temperature fluctuations.

Experimental set-up of the bio-digester is illustrated in Figure 1 while the experimental procedure is illustrated in Figure 2.

- . The experimental set-up consisted of a plastic bio-digester of about 82 liters capacity, equipped with features listed as follows:
 - i. Inlet and outlet control valves (ball valves) for controlling the feeding and removal rate of organic substrate from the bio-digester. In other words, feedstock was fed into the bio-digester through the inlet valve opening while the substrate after digestion was removed from the digester through the outlet valve opening.
 - ii. Gas extraction hose (4-inch in diameter) for evacuation of biogas from the system.
 - iii. Thermometer for measuring temperature variation during decomposition of organic feedstock inside the bio-digester.
 - iv. pH meter for measuring the pH of feedstock before, during and after digestion of organic feedstock.

- v. Deflated bicycle tube of about 500 g for storing of biogas generated from the system which flows into the rubber tube and causes it to inflate. At saturated pressure, biogas generated in the bio-digester flows through the gas extraction hose into the deflated tube where it is inflated.

Figure 1: Bio-digester equipment for experimental anaerobic digestion

Figure 2: experimental illustration of biogas recovery process

3. Results and Discussions

Results of Anaerobic digestion from single organic feedstock are presented in Table 1, whereas, the results of anaerobic digestion from multiple organic feedstock are presented in Table 2. These results were obtained from the step-by-step experimental procedures reported on the methodology of this study. The results were further represented through graphical illustrations and further analysis to identify the key findings of the study.

Table 1: Results of Anaerobic digestion from single organic feedstock

Evacuation Period	Evacuation Time								
	Time (10:00 am)			Time (2:00 pm)			Time (6:00 pm)		
	Mass = 80.2 kg, pH Range 6.8 to 7.2, HRT = 28								
Week 1 (Quantity of biogas in grams)	Yield	Tem	pH	Yield	Tem	pH	Yield	Tem	pH
	0.03	27	6.8	0.04	26.4	6.8	0.03	27.1	6.8
	0.03	27	6.8	0.02	27.3	6.9	0.02	27.3	6.8
	0.04	26.4	6.9	0.02	27.3	6.8	0.03	27.1	6.8
	0.03	27	6.8	0.01	27.5	7.1	0.02	27.3	6.9
	0.02	27.3	7.1	0.02	27.3	7.1	0.02	27.3	7.1
	0.02	27.3	6.9	0.02	27.3	6.9	0.01	27.5	6.9
	0.01	27.5	7.1	0.01	27.5	7.1	0.01	27.5	6.9
Week 2 (Quantity of biogas in grams)	0.1	27.5	6.9	0.1	27.6	6.9	0.1	27.6	6.9
	0.1	27.5	6.9	0.1	27.6	7.1	0.1	27.6	7.1
	0.13	27.6	6.9	0.14	27.7	7.1	0.14	27.7	6.9
	0.16	27.7	7.1	0.16	27.8	7.1	0.17	27.8	7.1
	0.17	27.7	7.1	0.17	27.8	7.1	0.18	27.9	7.1
	0.18	27.8	7.2	0.18	27.9	7.2	0.18	27.9	7.2
	0.18	27.8	7.1	0.19	27.9	7.2	0.19	27.9	7.1
Week 3 (Quantity of biogas in grams)	0.19	27.8	7.1	0.20	28	7.1	0.20	28.2	7.2
	0.21	28	6.9	0.21	28.4	7.2	0.21	28.5	7.1
	0.21	28	7.2	0.21	28.4	6.9	0.21	28.5	7.2
	0.21	28	7.1	0.21	28.4	7.1	0.21	28.5	6.9
	0.21	28	7.2	0.21	28.4	7.2	0.21	28.5	7.2
	0.22	29	7.2	0.22	28.7	7.2	0.22	29	7.2
	0.21	28	7.2	0.21	28.4	7.2	0.21	28.5	7.2
Week 4 (Quantity of biogas in grams)	0.21	28	6.8	0.21	28.4	6.8	0.21	28.5	6.8
	0.20	27.9	6.9	0.20	28	6.8	0.20	28.2	6.8
	0.17	27.7	6.9	0.17	27.8	6.9	0.14	27.7	6.8
	0.14	27.6	6.8	0.14	27.7	6.8	0.10	27.6	6.8
	0.10	27.5	6.8	0.10	27.6	6.8	0.08	26.7	6.8
	0.08	26.7	6.9	0.08	26.7	6.9	0.05	26.4	6.9
	0.04	26.4	6.8	0.03	26.2	6.9	0.01	26	6.8
Units	Temperature = °C, HRT = days								

Table 2: Results of Anaerobic digestion from multiple organic feedstock

Evacuation Period	Evacuation Time								
	Time (10:00 am)			Time (2:00 pm)			Time (6:00 pm)		
	Mass = 80.2 kg, pH Range 6.8 to 7.3, HRT = 28								
	Yield	Tem	pH	Yield	Tem	pH	Yield	Tem	pH
Week 1 (Quantity of biogas in grams)	0.04	28	6.8	0.06	27.4	6.8	0.05	28.2	6.8
	0.04	28	6.8	0.03	28.3	6.9	0.03	28.4	6.8
	0.05	27.4	6.9	0.03	28.3	6.8	0.04	28.1	6.8
	0.04	28	6.8	0.02	28.5	7.1	0.03	28.3	6.9
	0.03	28.2	7.1	0.03	28.3	7.1	0.03	28.3	7.1
	0.03	28.3	6.9	0.03	28.3	6.9	0.02	28.5	6.9
	0.01	28.6	7.1	0.01	28.5	7.1	0.01	28.5	6.9
Week 2 (Quantity of biogas in grams)	0.2	29.5	6.9	0.2	29.6	6.9	0.2	28.6	6.9
	0.2	29.5	6.9	0.2	29.6	7.1	0.21	29.6	7.1
	0.14	29.6	6.9	0.16	29.7	7.1	0.15	29.7	6.9
	0.17	29.7	7.1	0.17	29.8	7.1	0.18	29.8	7.1
	0.18	29.7	7.1	0.18	29.8	7.1	0.19	29.9	7.1
	0.19	29.8	7.2	0.19	29.9	7.2	0.20	29.9	7.2
	0.20	29.8	7.1	0.20	29.9	7.2	0.20	29.9	7.1
Week 3 (Quantity of biogas in grams)	0.21	30.8	7.1	0.21	30	7.1	0.22	30.2	7.2
	0.22	30	6.9	0.22	30.2	7.2	0.23	30.5	7.1
	0.22	30	7.2	0.22	30.4	6.9	0.23	30.4	7.2
	0.22	30	7.1	0.22	30.3	7.1	0.23	30.4	6.9
	0.22	30	7.2	0.22	30.4	7.3	0.24	30.5	7.2
	0.23	31	7.3	0.23	31	7.3	0.24	31	7.3
	0.23	30	7.3	0.23	30.3	7.3	0.24	30.5	7.3
Week 4 (Quantity of biogas in grams)	0.21	28	6.8	0.21	28.4	6.8	0.21	28.5	6.8
	0.20	27.9	6.9	0.20	28	6.8	0.20	28.2	6.8
	0.17	27.7	6.9	0.17	27.8	6.9	0.14	27.7	6.8
	0.14	27.6	6.8	0.14	27.7	6.8	0.10	27.6	6.8
	0.10	27.5	6.8	0.10	27.6	6.8	0.08	26.7	6.8
	0.08	26.7	6.9	0.08	26.7	6.9	0.05	26.4	6.9
	0.04	26.4	6.8	0.03	26.2	6.9	0.01	26	6.8
Units	Temperature = °C, HRT = days								

Figure 3a-b compares biogas yield profiles from two feedstock configurations (single feedstock and multiple feedstock) over varying Hydraulic Retention Times (HRT) and at different daily evacuation times: 10:00 am, 2:00 pm, and 6:00 pm. The comparison examines production trends, peak performance, ramp-up speed, and the effect of evacuation time on measured yields. At the initial phase (Days 1-8) for the single feedstock, biogas yields remained low (≤ 0.05 g) with slight fluctuations and a near-zero dip between days 4-7. For the ramp-up phase (Days 9-14), gradual increase was observed from 0.10 g to 0.20 g, with all times following a similar curve but 6:00 pm slightly higher. A stable trend on biogas yield was observed at a peak phase (Days 15-21) ranging from 0.21 to 0.22 g, with minor differences between times. Subsequently, decline phase (Days 22-27) characterized by a sharp drop in biogas yield was observed, which was more rapid for 10:00 am and 2:00 pm readings. However, for initial phase (Days 1-8) of multiple feedstock, early biogas yields were slightly higher than single feedstock (0.03-0.06 g), with a sharp dip to near zero at day 8. The ramp-up phase (Days 9-11) exhibited a steep

increase to 0.20 g in just 2-3 days, faster than single feedstock. The peak phase (Days 12-21) was observed to stabilize at 0.23-0.24 g, higher than single feedstock. For the decline phase (Days 22-28), slower drop-off was noticed, retaining higher yields for longer duration. Average yield was recorded between 8-10% higher than single feedstock across all times, with fastest ramp-up noticed at 6:00 pm in the multiple feedstock system (0.07 g/day).

Figure 3a: Plot of biogas yield against HRT from single feedstock

Figure 3b: Plot of biogas yield against HRT from multiple feedstock

Figure 4a-b compares bio-digester temperature profiles from two feedstock configurations (single feedstock and multiple feedstock) over varying HRT at different time intervals: 10:00 am, 2:00 pm, and 6:00 pm. Bio-digester loaded with single feedstock typically ranges from 26.0 to 29.0 °C across all times, with pick value of 29.0 °C, and characterized by sharp spike around day 18-19. The curve indicates slow rise from the beginning unto day 12-16, afterwards, a brief increase around mid-HRT, then decline to 26–26.5 °C by the end. However, Bio-digester loaded with multiple feedstock typically ranges from 26.0 to 31.5 °C across all times, with pick value approximately 31.0-31.5 °C, and characterized by sustained increase from day 11-20 with a slightly higher spike. The curve indicates an initial rapid increase to a sustained level in the mid HRT, then steeper decline towards the end of HRT. Therefore, bio-digester temperature with multiple feedstock showed higher average temperatures, a clearer average and higher peak temperatures compared to bio-digester with single-feedstock.

Additionally, bio-digester temperature with multiple feedstock indicate more balanced substrate mix, improved microbial activity and heat generation, better buffering of inhibitory compounds. However, bio-digester with single feedstock produced lower absolute temperatures and larger relative fluctuations particularly during the warmest period and towards the end of the run. Daily differences (10:00 vs 14:00 vs 18:00) are insignificant compared to multi-day trends because digesters have thermal inertia, but the afternoon (14:00) readings are slightly higher indicating a small diurnal ambient and metabolic heat effect.

Figure 4a: Plot of bio-digester temperature against HRT from single feedstock

Figure 4b: Plot of bio-digester temperature against HRT from multiple feedstock

Figure 5a-b compares bio-digester temperature and biogas yield from two feedstock configurations (single feedstock and multiple feedstock) over varying HRT at 10:00 am time interval. Bio-digester charged with single feedstock indicated low initial biogas yield from days 0-6, which gradually increased from days 7-18 and attended a peak yield ranging from 0.20-0.22 g around days 18-22, followed by decline to near-zero around day 28-30. Bio-digester charged with multi-feedstock revealed rapid initial increase in biogas yield, sustained peak yield from 0.20-0.24 g at mid-HRT and temperature ranging from 30-31 °C. The curve indicate increase in biogas yield with early abrupt spike from day 9-10, through mid-HRT (days 10-22), and sharp decline toward day 28.

Bio-digester temperature at of 10:00 am, for single feedstock was recorded as 26.2–28.0 °C while mid-HRT was around 27.5–28.0 °C, whereas, bio-digester temperature ranging from 27.0-31.5 °C, with 30–31 °C observed at mid-HRT for bio-digester with multiple feedstock. Biogas yield and bio-digester temperature correlated in both cases, with higher microbial activity, higher metabolic heat, higher temperature, higher biogas yield.

Bio-digester with multiple feedstock indicate greater productivity and stability overall but also a couple of abrupt spikes (likely feeding pulses or measurement/operational events), while the single feedstock bio-digester exhibits a slower rise and lower maxima. Microbiologically, bio-digester with multiple feedstock most likely underwent increased hydrolytic and methanogenic activity due to adequate substrate balance, trace nutrients as well as complementary carbon fractions, resulting in significant heat and biogas yield.

Figure 5a: Biogas yield and bio-digester temp from single feedstock @ 10:00 am

Figure 5b: Biogas yield and bio-digester temp from multiple feedstock @ 10:00 am

Figure 6a-b and Figures 7a-b compares bio-digester temperature and biogas yield from two feedstock configurations (single feedstock and multiple feedstock) over varying HRT at 2 pm and 6 pm am time interval.

Bio-digester temperature at 2 pm and 6 pm from single and multiple feedstock ranged from 26.5–28.8 °C (mid-HRT 27–28.5) and pH (6.8–7) as well as 27.5–31.5 °C (mid-HRT ≈ 30–31) and pH (6.8–7.3). Bio-digester charged with multiple feedstock revealed faster ramp-up, higher peak biogas yield, and higher sustained temperatures (mid-HRT ranged from 29.5–31.5 °C) compared to single feedstock temperature sustained from 27–28.8 °C. Biogas yields as indicated in Figures 6&7a-b increased concurrently with bio-digester temperature, possibly due to increased microbial activities.

The slightly wider pH range in the multiple feedstock (up to 7.3) configuration offered marginally more buffering and better methanogen activity, but higher pH at higher temperature can lead to increase in free (un-ionized) ammonia risk if TAN is high. The multiple feedstock digester is observed to offer a combination of labile and more improved substrates, which energises redundant microbial consortium, improves hydrolytic enzyme coverage, while providing significant syntrophic interactions between acidogens and methanogens. Labile fractions are responsible for accelerated hydrolysis and acidogenesis, providing significant substrate nutrients for methanogens which results in higher heat and biogas yield.

However, single feedstock (especially if lignified or low in available carbon fractions) hinders hydrolysis which consequently affects temperature increase and biogas yield. Methanogens prefer pH values ranging from 6.8–7.4, reflecting the pH range obtained from anaerobic digestion of single and multiple feedstock, which significantly favours methanogens.

Figure 6a: Biogas yield and bio-digester temp from single feedstock @ 2:00 pm

Figure 6b: Biogas yield and bio-digester temp from multiple feedstock @ 2:00 pm

Figure 7a: Biogas yield and bio-digester temp from single feedstock @ 6:00 pm

Figure 7b: Biogas yield and bio-digester temp from multiple feedstock @ 6:00 pm

4. Conclusion

Multiple feedstock outperformed single feedstock across all metrics, with higher average yield, higher peak yield, and longer sustained production. Multiple feedstock achieved peak biogas production nearly four times faster than single feedstock, due to higher microbial activity and substrate diversity benefits. In terms of evacuation time, 6:00 pm consistently yields the highest biogas volumes for both feedstocks. Difference between 6:00 pm and 10:00 am is small but consistent (0.005-0.01 g in average yield), suggesting cumulative gas build-up through the day, making later evacuation more productive. The bio-digester loaded with multiple feedstock offered higher and more stable temperatures (mid-HRT plateau 30-31 °C) and higher peaks,

consistent with improved microbial activity and co-digestion synergy. However, bio-digester with single feedstock remained warmer (26-29 °C), with more variability and likely lower methane productivity. Bio-digester charged with multiple feedstocks clearly indicates an improved biogas productivity and increased as well as sustained bio-digester temperature compared to bio-digester with single feedstock, likely due to increased microbial activity, broader nutrient availability and improved substrate balance. These benefits come with the common trade-offs such as the need to control OLR and watch for inhibition (VFAs, ammonia) at higher temperatures. However, with adequate monitoring and gradual feed management, multiple feedstocks combination provides a straightforward route to higher methane yields and better thermal performance. Hence, results obtained from this comparative study indicates a clear operational advantage of multiple feedstock co-digestion, including faster productivity and higher peaks, which supports stronger methanogenesis. The pH range for multiple feedstock digestion offers buffering advantage, but higher temperatures and pH may increase the tendency for free ammonia inhibition if TAN is high. However, with controlled feeding, monitoring, insulation and selective nutrient management, higher biogas output can be achieved with multiple feedstock.

References

- Amoo, A. O., Sabo, A., Haruna, A., Adeleye, A. O., Amoo, N. B., Ijanu, E. M., & Asaju, C. I. (2025). A Comparative Analysis of Cattle Rumen Content and Anaerobic Mono-and Co-digestion of Food Waste with Evidence from Microbial Communities, Biogas Yield, and Redox Potential. In *Energy Transition, Climate Action and Sustainable Agriculture: Perspectives and Strategies for Africa* (pp. 437-461). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Bewani, R., Nassour, A., Böning, T., Sprafke, J., & Nelles, M. (2025). Assessing the Impact of Residual Municipal Solid Waste Characteristics on Screw Press Performance in a Mechanical Biological Treatment Plant Optimized with Anaerobic Digestion. *Sustainability*, 17(14), 6365.
- Borhany, H. (2025). Converting Organic Municipal Solid Waste into Volatile Fatty Acids and Biogas: Experimental Pilot and Batch Studies With Statistical Analysis. *JMIRx Med*, 6:e50458.
- Dasgupta, A. (2025). Anaerobic digestion solutions: advancing circular economy goals in emerging economies. *Waste-to-Energy*, 3, 47-65.
- Dhaouefi, Z., Lecoublet, M., Taktek, S., Lafontaine, S., LeBihan, Y., Braghiroli, F. L., Horchani, H., & Koubaa, A. (2025). A Review of Operational Conditions of the Agroforestry Residues Biomethanization for Bioenergy Production through Solid-State Anaerobic Digestion (SS-AD). *Energies*, 18(6), 1397.
- Ebunilo, P. O., Okovido, J., & Ikpe, A. E. (2018). Investigation of the Energy (Biogas) Production from Co-Digestion of Organic Waste Materials. *International Journal of Energy Applications and Technologies*, 5(2), 68-75.
- El-Sheikh, H. M., Gammal, Y. O. E., & Ahmad, S. S. (2025). Optimizing Food Waste Digestion: A Review of Parameters and Pre-treatment Techniques. *Egyptian Journal of Petroleum*, 34(2), 4.
- Eronmosele, P., Akhiero, T. E., & Ikpe, A. E., (2020). Comparative Study of the Kinetics of Biogas Yield from the Co-digestion of Poultry Droppings with Waterleaf and Poultry Droppings with Elephant Grass. *Engineering Sciences*, 15(3), 139-150.

- Ezeh, E. M., Agu, P. C., & Aworabhi, E. (2024). Biological Treatment Techniques for Sewage: Aerobic and Anaerobic. *Sewage-Management and Treatment Techniques*: Intech Open Limited, London, United Kingdom.
- Gabanki, M. R., Yousefi, H., Hajinezhad, A., Abdoos, M., & Mohammaddini, S. (2025). Innovative approaches to biohydrogen production from organic waste: pathways and sustainability challenges. *Waste Management Bulletin*, 100227.
- Griggs, A. T., Roulier, A., Granda, N. A., & Burek, J. (2025). Life cycle assessments of residual hemp biomass from cannabidiol production focusing on disposal pathways and biomethane recovery via anaerobic digestion. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 223, 108525.
- Grobelak, A., Bień, B., Sławczyk, D., & Bień, J. (2025). Conditioning Biomass for Biogas Plants: Innovative Pre-Treatment and Digestate Valorization Techniques to Enhance Soil Health and Fertility. *Sustainability*, 17(8), 3289.
- Ibrahim, N. A., Majeed, H. H., Jwaid, T. A., & Silas, K. (2025). Advancements in anaerobic digestion of organic waste for sustainable biogas production. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 32(30):17916-17930.
- Ikpe, A. E., Ekanem, K. R., & Basse, M. O. (2024). Experimental investigation of biogas yielding rate from anaerobic codigestion of multiple organic feedstocks using a bio-digester. *Journal of Advances in Environmental Health Research*, 12(4), 228-239.
- Ikpe, A. E., Imonitie, D. I., & Ndon, A. E. (2019). Investigation of Biogas Energy Derivation from Anaerobic Digestion of Different Local Food Wastes in Nigeria. *Academic Platform Journal of Engineering and Science*, 7-2, 332-340.
- Ikpe, A. E., Ndon, A. E., & Etim, P. J. (2020). Fuzzy Modelling and Optimization of Anaerobic Co-Digestion Process Parameters for Effective Biogas Yield from Bio-wastes. *The International Journal of Energy & Engineering Sciences*, 5(2), 43-61.
- Kabeyi, M. J. B., Akpan, J., & Olanrewaju, A. O. (2025). Electricity generation and multi-purpose applications from biogas and biomethane. *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive System*, 16(2), 1325-1340.
- Kamboj, N., Chugh, P., Wijenayake, W. P. T., Mitra, D., Panneerselvam, P., & Kumar, R. (2025). Multifunctionality and Diversity of Antagonistic Potential Fungi as Biocontrol Agent. In *Bio-control Agents for Sustainable Agriculture: Diversity, Mechanisms and Applications* (pp. 167-208). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
- Kim, D., & Kim, J. (2025). Predicting biogas production from organic waste through anaerobic co-digestion. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 496, 145122.
- Makondo, C. C., Gershom, M., & Rashama, C. (2025). A review of global treaties and agreements on greening the anaerobic digestion industry in the face of climate change. *Innovations in the Global Biogas industry*, 17, 473-494.
- Martín-Sanz-Garrido, C., Revuelta-Aramburu, M., Santos-Montes, A. M., & Morales-Polo, C. (2025). A Review on Anaerobic Digestate as a Biofertilizer: Characteristics, Production, and Environmental Impacts from a Life Cycle Assessment Perspective. *Applied Sciences*, 15(15), 8635.
- Milicevic, D. P. M., Chan, Y. J., Shi, S., & Thangalazhy-Gopakumar, S. (2025). Effect of torrefaction of palm frond on methane yield through anaerobic co-digestion with palm oil mill effluent. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis*, 192, 107316.
- Negro, V., Noussan, M., & Chiaramonti, D. (2025). Alternative options for biogas-to-energy: A comparison of electricity and biomethane generation based on the real operation of a production site. *Applied Energy*, 377, 124687.
- Ochuko M. O. (2025). Anaerobic Digestion for Wastewater Treatment: A Review of Principles, Processes and Performance. *Journal of Energy Technology and Environment*, 7(1) 52-60.

- Perera, H., Hosan, S., Vithanage, V., Wijesekara, D., Gunawardhana, N., Tharaka, V., & Abeysinghe, S. (2025). Review on Comparison of Single Stage and Multistage and Dry-Wet Anaerobic Digestion for Biomethane Production and Evaluation the Waste Management Strategy. *Radinka Journal of Science and Systematic Literature Review*, 3(1), 574-589.
- Qian, S., Chen, L., Xu, S., Zeng, C., Lian, X., Xia, Z., & Zou, J. (2025). Research on methane-rich biogas production technology by anaerobic digestion under carbon neutrality: A review. *Sustainability*, 17(4), 1425.
- Rhee, C., Cho, S., Kang, I., Bae, I., Cho, K., & Shin, S. G. (2025). Anaerobic co-digestion of tobacco processing residue: Multi-step approach for process optimization, key syntrophic microbiome identification, and techno-economic analysis. *Energy*, 319, 135119.
- Saelor, S., Kongjan, P., Prasertsan, P., Mamimin, C., & O-Thong, S. (2025). Enhancing the efficiency of high solid anaerobic digestion of empty fruit bunches under thermophilic conditions by particle size reduction and co-digestion with palm oil mill effluent. *Carbon Resources Conversion*, 8(2), 100262.
- Sani, M. N. H., Amin, M., Bergstrand, K. J., Caspersen, S., Prade, T., & Yong, J. W. H. (2025). Harnessing biostimulants from biogas digestates for high-value resource recovery: a review. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 23(1), 139-164.
- Serna-García, R., Martí, N., Serralta, J., & Ferrer, J. (2025). Biogas from Anaerobic Digestion. In *Hydrogen and Low-Carbon Fuels in Circular Bio-economy: Assessment Methodologies, Production Technologies and Sector-Specific Applications* (pp. 135-161). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Silva, I., Lapa, N., Ribeiro, H., & Duarte, E. (2025). Pig slurry anaerobic digestion: the role of biochar as an additive towards biogas and digestate improvement. *Applied Sciences*, 15(3), 1037.
- Simeonov, I., Chorukova, E., & Kabaivanova, L. (2025). Two-stage anaerobic digestion for green energy production: A review. *Processes*, 13(2), 294.
- Woźniak, A., Kuligowski, K., Świerczek, L., & Cenian, A. (2025). Review of lignocellulosic biomass pretreatment using physical, thermal and chemical methods for higher yields in bioethanol production. *Sustainability*, 17(1), 287.
- Zhu, M., Song, L., Li, W., Qin, Y., & Li, Y. Y. (2025). Hydraulic retention times as key parameter governing biomethanation of brewery spent grain and system stability in long-term continuously-feeding anaerobic digestion. *Bioresource Technology*, 425, 132331.